

Harmonic Decomposition and Power Quality Analysis of a Six-Phase Induction Motor Traction Drive with Fast Fourier Transform

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Abstract—This paper presents an analysis of harmonic decomposition and power quality analysis of a six-phase asynchronous motor drive model designed for traction systems, by the Fast Fourier Transform tool. The six-phase asynchronous motor is fed by a Voltage Source Inverter. The goal is to determine whether the proposed 6-phase traction system is viable to prototype and test from the standpoint of power quality and electromagnetic compatibility. The resulting power quality distortion by harmonics suggest that the proposed traction system generates acceptable distortions, through but for which the accepted FFT analysis, in the IEEE Standards 1459-2010 and 519-2014, is not an efficient tool for analysis of highly dynamic traction systems. For a good representation of power distortions, a different standard should be developed and employed

Keywords— multi-phase induction motor, Fourier transform, modeling, power quality, harmonics

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric traction is a growing interest in the transition of world economy to a sustainable path. Electric transportation is part of the sustainable cities and communities' goal [1].

The classic approach to electric traction to design traction systems for different transportation methods based on either a three-phase induction motor or permanent magnet motor, such as permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) or brushless direct current motor (BLDC).

The search for higher efficiency opens the door for other systems to be included in the discussion, one option is the multiphase induction motor (MIM). The advantages of the MIM have been discussed in previous works [2-4] and were good enough that the discussion on multiphase systems continues to this day. The advantages of higher reliability, higher torque, and necessity for lower power semiconductors for power converters for the same power level still drive the interest for implementing multiphase electric machines.

A reliable model of multiphase traction systems is the six-phase traction system (6PTS). It relies on a six-phase induction motor, with field-oriented control, designed and presented in [5], (Fig. 1), using the six phase - dq transformation [6]. The results showed good dynamic response, which is the main goal for electric traction systems.

On the other hand, the six phase electric drives presented a series of issues related to the increased losses due to harmonics [7]. The nonlinear load type of the power converter distorts the output currents from perfect sinusoids and enriching the harmonic spectrum. There are proposed filters for these consequences, and with the goal to increase power

quality. An improvement in these calculations must be done with testing the motor operation from in application specific load, as opposed to the no-load operation. In [8], the six-phase IM drive is tested in more situations, and topology, with clear understanding that the symmetrical distribution of phase windings is optimal for high frequency switching. Both papers considered constant rotor speed, and the steady state of the drive. This paper will consider the specific use case and load specifics of traction applications, with focus on the transient stages of drive functioning.

The aim of this study is to make an analysis of the waveform of stator current and voltage, by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), supplied to the IM's stator by mathematical modeling and simulation, as precursor to a prototype test. The IEEE standard 1459-2010 [9] provides the calculation method of the power components based on a frequency-domain approach using FFT, meaning these components are necessary in complying with the power quality standards, presented in IEEE standard 519-2014 [10]. This paper will show the gained results from using MATLAB Simulink environment for modelling the dynamics of the 6PTS, and the decomposition of the stator current by FFT into component harmonics

II. TRANSIENT STATE FFT ANALYSIS OF TRACTION DRIVE

The electric drive is driven by a test motor, designed for 2.2 kW output power, to connect to a six-phase voltage source of 220V. This is the motor design that will first be prototyped before prototyping the higher necessary power for urban traction.

The IM is fed by a 6 half-bridge voltage source inverter (VSI), presented in Fig. 1. The monitoring model of the six-phase IM is presented in Fig. 2.

For the model to be viable firstly will be presented the dynamic proprieties of the IM (Fig. 3). It can be observed that the dynamic response of the torque is acceptable, while a slight decrease in rotor angular velocity is present when the torque reference reaches the step variation. The switching frequency was set at 20kHz for the VSI.

The electrical parameters that characterize the functioning of the 6PTS are presented in TABLE I. Three of the voltages (the other three are symmetrical) are presented in Fig.4, and in Fig. 5 are presented the 6 current phases and an isolated current phase, which will be the basis for in detail analysis of the signal decomposition.

To conduct a harmonic decomposition analysis that would characterize the transient processes of traction systems, the

FFT analysis was performed from the start of the speed step, for 4 consecutive periods (see TABLE II), where the 4th period is considered stationary (as in Fig.5).

TABLE I. MAIN DATA OF INDUCTION MOTOR

Rated power, kW	2.2
Rated phase voltage, V	220
Rated supply frequency, Hz	50
Rated phase current, A	6.1
Phases	6
Pairs of poles	2

TABLE II. ANALYZED PERIODS

Stage	Time period
Transient 1	1 – 1.02 s
Transient 2	1.02 – 1.04 s
Transient 3	1.04 – 1.06 s
Steady	1.06 – 1.08 s

Fig. 1. Six half-bridge VSI of the model.

Fig. 2. Six-phase IM monitoring model.

Fig. 3. Motor mechanical characteristics.

Fig. 4. Stator voltage for first 3 phases.

Fig. 5. top – 6 Phases stator currents, bottom - stator current of a single phase.

III. TRANSIENT STATE FFT ANALYSIS OF TRACTION SYSTEM

The FFT analysis provides a lot of data that was analyzed in stages. In Fig. 6 is a general overview of the evolution of current and voltage total harmonic distortion (THD), per each time phase of the transient process. Each transient process represents one full period of 20 ms, which is the period for 50 Hz frequency signal.

The motor being symmetrical it can be observed that there are 3 lines of THD evolution for current, and 2 lines of THD evolution for voltage. Because of the step form of the speed as input reference to the drive control, the PWM duty cycle remains constant, with a constant THD at 119% (Fig.6). Even though it seems like a high value, to motor functioning and efficiency this does not influence greatly, because the currents are the physical values that contribute to the creation of magnetic fields, and electromagnetic torque.

The more important values for the 6PTS efficiency, are the currents on the motor phases. As can be seen in Fig.5, the first transient period, is most distorted compared to the steady state waveform, the same can be seen in Fig.6. Where the current THD drops from 20, 45 and 52%, on the 3 pairs of phases, to under 10% the next period for all phases. Thus, the next focus will be understanding the harmonic decomposition of the signal for the first 4 period in the current evolution. A thing to note when executing a FFT analysis on a signal is the starting phase. The huge differences in THD for the 1st transient stage is the currents having different starting angles, so rather than calculating the modules of the variable currents, the modeling relies on instantaneous values and phase angles. Second transient stage and later we see the values being much closer.

Fig. 6. All 6 phases FFT decomp, steady state, per simulation phase. Top – currents, bottom – voltages.

There is not a standard that imposes limits for THD for multiphase systems, but standard IEEE 519-2014 [9] gives recommendations of acceptable values for three-phase system THD, which is the closest standard for correlation. 519-2014 standard also suggests recommendations in the steady state, while the values in transient state may exceed the recommendations. The recommended limit for THD for low voltages ($\leq 1\text{kV}$) is 8% and for any single voltage harmonic is 5%. Since the ratio between the short circuit current and maximum demand load current is below 20 ($I_{sc}/I_L < 20$), then the standards recommend the following maximum values for THD: 4% for harmonic orders (HOs) from 3 to 11; 2% for HOs from 11 to 17, 1.5% for HOs from 17 to 23, 0.6% for HOs from 23 to 35 and 0.3% for HOs from 35 to 50. It's important to mention that these values are correlated to higher periods of analysis of 3 s and more.

In steady state, the FFT analysis of one phase provided a THD of 3.33% (Fig. 7, 8), which is compliant with the recommended values. On the other hand, FFT analysis of one phase in transient state provided a THD of 20.89%, 5.29% and 3.68% for three consecutive transient periods (Fig. 9-11) and was shown that these values exceed the recommended limits, as was expected. This problem can be solved by using external filtering.

Fig. 7. Single phase current decomp, steady state, up to HO 70.

Fig. 8. Single phase current decomp, steady state, HOs 180 – 420.

Fig. 9. Single phase current decomp, transient 1.

Fig. 10. Single phase current decomp, transient 2.

Fig. 11. Single phase current decomp, transient 3.

An important observation for the harmonic analysis of currents and voltage is the order of harmonics present. The presence of current HOs that are multiple of three showed an asymmetry in the power converter. Also, values for HOs $6*n\pm 1$ ($n=1,2,3\dots$) were higher which was expected for a 6-phase motor. These harmonics provide essential insight into the efficiency of the 6PTS, specifically harmonics of orders $(6*n-1)$ ($n=1,2,3\dots$) provide braking torques in the motor, while $(6*n+1)$ HOs provide accelerating torque.

In TABLE III, it can be observed that DC and 2nd order harmonics are excessive at the 1st transient stage, which is natural considering current's waveform (Fig. 5); and are quickly diminished even at the next period. The 5th harmonic, on the other hand, maintains a high value during all functioning. The 5th harmonic being in the harmonic family $(6*n-1)$, presents an obvious decrease of output efficiency due to these harmonics.

In Fig.12 are presented the harmonic weight for the transient stages and the steady state, to understand the variation of harmonic spectra of current waveform in the transient processes. Understandably, where transient states are much more frequent, such as the traction and propulsion of vehicles and mobile devices, they are of higher impact in overall efficiency of the drive. Such mobile systems usually require vital necessity in efficient energy consumption to ensure longer autonomous work, where necessary.

Looking at the frequency of the high order harmonics in steady state for current (Fig.8), as well as voltage (Fig.13-16), it must be mentioned that there are significant clusters of harmonics. For currents the cluster is centered around HO 200 and 400, corresponding to 10 kHz and 20 kHz, reach weights of up to 0.15% of the fundamentals. For voltages, the clusters are centered around HOs 400 and 800, corresponding to 20 kHz and 40 kHz of much more significant weight, up to 75% (Fig.15) and 30% (Fig.16), of the fundamental 50 Hz signal. Considering that electric energy circulating is proportional to the product of current and voltage, the significant HO for both current and voltage to consider is HO 400, which corresponds to the switching frequency of the 6 phased VSI, subsequently the harmonics in Fig. 8 and Fig. 15 require a dedicated filter, to suppress these harmonics.

Fig. 12 Single phase current THD, top – for the transient stages 1 and 3; bottom – steady state.

Fig. 13 Single phase voltage decomposition, steady state.

Fig. 14 Single phase voltage decomposition, steady state, harmonics 0 – 100.

TABLE III. FIRST 5 HARMONICS IN A SINGLE-PHASE CURRENT OF THE 6PTS, PER ANALYZED TIME PERIOD

		Transient 1	Transient 2	Transient 3	Steady
THD, %		20.89	5.29	3.68	3.32
Fund ampl., A		4.311	7.851	6.82	7.025
Harmonic Order	Frequency	Weight, %	Weight, %	Weight, %	Weight, %
0	0	30.26	6.382	1.294	0.032
1	50	100	100	100	100
2	100	18.037	2.585	0.696	0.019
3	150	6.321	1.878	0.589	0.075
4	200	3.291	1.451	0.449	0.008
5	250	6.728	2.754	3.09	2.963
13	650	2.297	1.201	1.261	1.226

Fig. 15 Single phase voltage decomposition, steady state, harmonics 350 – 480.

Fig. 16 Single phase voltage decomposition, steady state, harmonics 780 – 825.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, harmonic analysis and power quality analysis were employed for a six-phase asynchronous motor drive model designed for traction systems. The motor was modeled in MATLAB using the real data of a motor and was controlled by a VSI. The method used for signal decomposition is FFT. The decomposition showed good results in steady-state, and the THD values did not exceed the recommended standard values. On the other hand, the transient state values were higher than recommended and this problem must be addressed in development of new standards and solved by reducing THD by employing external filtering.

It is important to mention the fact that the use of FFT analysis is mostly limited to steady-state signals because it applies a principle of fixed sliding window and assumes half-period symmetry for faster analysis. This means low computational burden, but the backlash of the sliding window is spectral leakage, aliasing, loss of time information and other problems. For transient state authors propose for the future scope of work the application of other methods than the

standard recommended FFT, such as double Fourier series that is often used for harmonic calculations in power converters, or Wavelet transform which can preserve both time and frequency information and uses high and low-pass filters for decomposition and changes the width of the window which makes it suitable for transient analysis.

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